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A new meteorological pressure index for environmental feasibility analyses of geographical sites on regional scale eligible to install an incinerator plant

Technical Report

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Abstract. To date, incinerator facilities should meet very strict criteria for emission levels and environmental impacts connected to releases of pollutants into atmosphere must be reduced taking advantage of transport phenomena connected to effects of wind fields on large scale areas. As a reply, a new Meteorological Pressure Index was developed to identify sites, on regional scale, with resilience in terms of transport phenomena correlated to natural wind actions. By using a fuzzy approach, MPI combines data of 3D wind speed, its direction and frequency for geographical areas of interest as well as designs maps usefully to perform environmental feasibility analyses. MPI application in Sicily region, Italy, has allowed to identify those bordering areas that would have a higher effectiveness in pollutant transport. These results allow to open the way for the use of MPI in environmental feasibility analyses concerning other facilities in the process industry that produce atmospheric pollution.

Introduction

As part of a collaboration between Regional Agency of Environmental Protection in Sicily (ARPA) and Department of Engineering, University of Palermo, research activities were performed about classification of wind measure stations subsets useful to support exchange information among EU member states as stated (European Commission 97/101/CE, 27th January 1997) (ARPA 2018, 2019; Giardina et al., 2019).

These activities allowed to develop, by the way, a new meteorological pressure index (MPI) useful to identify geographical sites, on regional scale, with resilience capacity in terms of transport phenomena connected to natural wind actions.

In this paper, MPI is proposed as a tool to identify sites that can be classified appropriate for example to installation of an incineration plant and so to aid decision-making process. In recent years, landfill waste disposal are replaced progressively by processes that allow the recovery of materials and energy, according to the European directives (e.g., 2008/98/CE).

Waste-to-energy incinerators are waste treatment facilities able to convert municipal solid waste into energy, generating gas and particle matter (PM) emissions (Quina et al., 2011; Conca et al., 2020).

From this it follows that incinerator facilities have to meet very strict criteria for the emission levels. What is more, the environmental impacts connected to releases of pollutants into atmosphere must be reduced taking advantage of the best features of transport phenomena connected to wind fields on large scale areas. So, it becomes crucial to perform in-depth environmental feasibility studies and to find out those geographical sites that has a natural predisposition to transport connected with intense wind flows.

As a reply to this need, MPI allows to integrate data of 3D wind speed, its direction and frequency for the geographical areas of interest and the creation of map-making usefully to perform environmental feasibility analyses. Therefore, by resorting to a single index, it is possible have a tool useful to identify neighbouring areas on large scale that are characterized by environmental similarities in term of 3D wind fields (specifically, zones high rates of air interchange against zones absence of any interchange). In addition, this tool comes in handy to define information that can link impacts with maps, for example, related to emission sources in regional air pollution modelling.

MPI application in Sicily region, Italy, as a case study, has allowed to identify areas with high efficiency from the pollutant transport point of view. In the last few years, the management of waste produced in this region has become a pressing concern that the authorities intend to solve through the construction of an incinerator. So, it is very important to create accurate feasibility analyses as a first phase of decision-making resources as well as to provide answers to society's perception of the acceptability of the risk for this type of facility.

This study has allowed to identify zones highly predisposed to stand up in a natural manner against the pollution and areas that are eligible to house an incinerator plant taking into account zones classified as special protection Natura 2000 or hydrologic and seismic vulnerability.

It is worth highlighting that these results allow to open the way towards the use of the tool proposed in this paper for environmental feasibility analyses concerning other facilities in the process industry that produce atmospheric pollution, offering a point of view useful to support the decision making.

1. Fuzzy logic and fuzzy operations

Fuzzy logic and Fuzzy sets (Zadeh, 1975; 1992; Pedrycz, 1996) have found an important role in different fields (Oke, 2004; Castiglia et al. 2008, 2010, 2011, 2015; Casamirra et al., 2009; Mahmoudi et al., 2019; Kentel and Aral, 2004, 2007; Sadiq and Tesfamariam, 2009; Turskis et al., 2012; Heydari et al., 2018). Applications can be found also in different meteorological and environmental analyses (Cao and Chen, 1983; Shepard, 2005; Liu et al. 2009; Ghobadi and Jafari, 2015; Abdourahamane and Acar, 2018; Heydari et al., 2018; Saffari et al. 2019; Sardar et al., 2020).

This approach allows to deal with problems characterised by imprecise phenomena or to model experiences defined by linguistic expressions.

As well known, classic set theory is based on bivalent logic. A shortcoming of this approach is its inability to come to grips with the issue of uncertainty and imprecision.

On the contrary, let Ω be a collection of fuzzy objects (i.e. universe of discourse) whose elements are denoted by x ; a fuzzy subset A in Ω is characterized by a membership function $f_A(x)$ that associates x in Ω with a real number in interval $[0, 1]$ (Zadeh, 1975). Function $f_A(x)$ is the membership degree of x in A .

The most common fuzzy membership functions are triangular or trapezoidal (Giardina et al., 2019).

Zadeh (1975) suggested for operations on fuzzy sets, minimum operator for intersection and the maximum operator for union:

$$A \cap B \equiv \{ \langle x, f_{A \cap B}(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \text{ e } f_{A \cap B}(x) = \min[f_A(x), f_B(x)] \} \quad (1)$$

$$A \cup B \equiv \{ \langle x, f_{A \cup B}(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \text{ e } f_{A \cup B}(x) = \max[f_A(x), f_B(x)] \} \quad (2)$$

The combination of these two operators is generally used for the definition of *fuzzy if-then* rules, i.e. the fuzzy inference system (FIS) characterized by the following main steps (Fig. 1):

- Fuzzification process to change crisp value into fuzzy sets;
- Construction of FIS, based on if-then rules where fuzzy logic operations are used to determine fuzzy

outputs;

- Defuzzification process to return from fuzzy numbers to crisp value.

An example of fuzzy *if-then* rules is reported below:

$$\text{Rule: If } y_1 \text{ is } A_{i1} \text{ and } \dots \text{ and } y_n \text{ is } A_{in} \text{ then } y \text{ is } B_i \quad i=1, 2, \dots, m \quad (w_i) \quad (3)$$

where A_{ij} and B_i are input and output linguistic variables of universes of discourse Ω and w_i is the importance degree of the rule, in the interval $[0, 1]$.

The *if*-part of the " x_n is A_{jn} " rule it's called antecedent, or assumption, while the *then*-part of the " y is B_j " rule it's called consequent.

The parameter w_i in Eq. (3), that gives the weight attributed at rule if compared to the other rules in the FIS system, allows the analyst to attribute an importance level to each rule.

If min-max inference is used in fuzzy *if-then* rules of Eq. (3), Eq. (2) is employed in *if* parts of the rule (i.e., intersection) and Eq. (3) is used to aggregate output fuzzy sets (i.e., union) after cutting output membership functions at the minimum values of the antecedents ((Kundu,1998; Giardina et al., 2014).

If Eq. (3) is used with the attribution of a weight, the consequent function B_j is modified as follow:

$$f_i^*(x) = \max \{w_i f_i(x); \text{ for } i=1, 2, \dots, m\} \quad (4)$$

If min-max inference (Kundu,1998) is used in fuzzy *if-then* rules then Eq. (3) is employed in *if* parts of each rule (i.e., intersection) and Eq. (4) is used to aggregate output fuzzy sets (i.e., union) after cutting output membership functions at the minimum values of the antecedents (Giardina et al., 2014).

Final step is the defuzzification procedure that consists of averaging the fuzzy outputs into a single decision (crisp value) (Ramli and Mohamad, 2009; Castiglia and Giardina, 2011; Giardina et al., 2014; Castiglia et al., 2015), i.e.:

$$\text{Crisp} = \frac{\int x f^*(x) dx}{\int f^*(x) dx} \quad (5)$$

where $f^*(x)$ is calculated by using Eq. (4).

2. Fuzzy MPI index

Fuzzy classification is a process that allows to group elements, having the same characteristics, in a fuzzy set. As stated above, it corresponds to assign a membership function that indicates whether an element is a member of a class, given its fuzzy classification predicate.

For MPI index, two fuzzy pressure indicators are classified, i.e.:

- wind speed (WS) [m/s];
- percentage of wind frequency (WF) [%].

Fuzzy classifications of WSI and WF are built by using the fuzzy linguistic approach reported in (Giardina et al., 2019). Note that WS is classified taking into account the Beaufort scale (Barua, 2005), based on observed conditions at sea or on land of wind speeds.

By using the approach described in (Giardina et al., 2014), 75 FIS rules for MPI (25 rules for each of the three layers with which the vertical wind fields is schematized) are developed. To do this, weights of each linguistic term is evaluated by assuming linear hypothesis as follows:

$$p_{WS}, p_{WF}, p_{MPI} = i/k \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k \quad (6)$$

where k is the number of language variables that define WS, WF and MPI.

Linguistic terms and weights obtained by Eq. (6) for WS, WF and MPI, used in this paper, are reported in Tab.s (1) through (3).

More details about the fuzzy approach used to define the fuzzy *if-then* rule is described in the following section.

2.1 Example of determination of fuzzy rule-based system for MPI index

Let us take input fuzzy sets of WS and WF, pertinent weights reported in Tab.s 1 and 2, and MPI fuzzy outputs and related weights reported in Tab. 3.

Fuzzy *if-then* rules are determined taking into account the relative importance of the input variables WS and WF that is set to $R_{WSI} = 0.5$ and $R_{WFI} = 0.5$ for the first vertical layer of the 3D domain.

In more detail, MPI output linguistic term, to be used within fuzzy *if-then* rule, is identified by using weight p_{MPI} calculated by using the following relationship:

$$p_{MPI} = R_{WS} p_{WS} + R_{WF} p_{WF} \quad (7)$$

On the basis of the above equation, it is possible to identify the following rule:

Rule: *If* WS is VL with $p_{WS} = 0.2$ **and** WF is M with $p_{WF} = 0.6$ **then** MPI is Between Low and Medium (L_M) with $p_{MPI} = 0.444$ (8)

Detailing the content of the above rule, by using Eq. (7) mathematically it happens that $p_{MPI} = 0.5 \times 0.2 + 0.5 \times 0.6 = 0.4$. This value is close to MPI impact defined as Between Low and Medium (L_M) (Tab. 3) with weight $p_{RPN} = 0,444$.

If the calculation is performed for subsequent two vertical layers, relative importance parameters are assumed $R_{WS} = 0.4$ and $R_{WF} = 0.6$ to emphasize pressures due to wind frequency WF. This is made because frictional drags have low impact on wind speed in higher vertical layers compared to frictional drags in the first layer (or ground level); consequently, more subtle differences can be observed among neighboring zones in terms of wind speed values, therefore wind frequency is the meteorological situation that better follows reciprocal exchanges among neighbouring areas.

Min-max inference, described in section 1, has been used as aggregation in *if-then* procedure to combine input fuzzy sets into output fuzzy sets.

Defuzzification step is carried out by using the relationship reported in Eq. (5).

Note that MPI index is calculated in each cell neighboring of a generic cell $c[i,j]$, as represented in Fig. 2, and sum of the results is attributed to $c[i,j]$. This allows to take into account two main factors: $c[i,j]$ receives

meteorological pressure from the nearby cells; wind directions (i.e., direction bins: North, NE, East, SE, South, SW, West, and NW) that with more frequency affect $c[i,j]$.

2.2 MPI evaluation by using CALMET simulation

Fig. 3 reports a flow chart of the procedure developed for computing MPI index. Different pre-processing tools are used to elaborate observed meteorological data and land use information to be used in the CALMET code (Scire et al., 1995, 2000).

As is known, CALMET is a meteorological model that develops hourly wind and temperature fields on a three-dimensional gridded modeling domain, and two-dimensional fields of turbulent parameters.

Like all the diagnostic models, it can extrapolate three-dimensional meteorological data, starting from a sufficient number of measurements on the ground, taking into account site's orographic characteristics and any physical constraints.

The diagnostic wind field module uses a two-step approach to reconstruct the final wind field:

- Step 1, an initial guess wind field is adjusted to take into account kinematic effects of terrain, slope flows, and terrain blocking effects;
- Step 2, an objective analysis procedure is used to introduce observational data in the wind field generated in the first step and to produce the final three-dimensional wind field.

In the first step, prognostic data simulated by model like WRF (Weather Research and Forecasting model) or Mesoscale Model (MM5) can be used in three different ways:

- replacement of the initial guess field;
- replacement of the Step 1 field;
- use as pseudo-observations in the objective analysis procedure.

Micrometeorological model in CALMET uses, for the sensible heat flux computing on the ground, models reported in (Holtslag and Van Ulden, 1982, 1983) and Monin-Obukhov length. Micrometeorological parameters are used to compute the PBL (planetary boundary layer) thickness and useful coefficients for the application of the turbulent dispersion model.

MPI computing is done for each of the first three vertical layers which, in CALMET simulations, schematize atmospheric conditions at altitude of 10, 20, 40 m.

A pre-processing algorithm, written in R-cran (MPI.r in Fig. 3), allows to process CALMET results and creates input necessary for the fuzzy model application. Velocity and frequency wind values attributed by CALMET to the eight cells adjacent to the cell $c[i,j]$ (Fig. 2), are used as inputs in the fuzzy inference process and sum of results is assigned to $c[i,j]$, creating a map that can be used, for example, in QGIS software.

Finally, a MPI normalization procedure is done by using a distribution in ten quantiles, as suggested in (OECD, 2008).

3. Application of MPI in a case study and results

Sicily is in the middle of the Mediterranean Sea and generally does face hot dry summers and mild winters with hardly any frost.

Because of its position, it is in a transition area between dry and arid climate typically of North Africa and more temperate climate of central Europe. Therefore, the region is often affected by phenomena activated by interactions between processes typical of middle latitudes (Castorina et al., 2021). In summer, moist convective phenomena lead to thunderstorm that affects the inland areas, where temperature can reach high values. In autumn, the seas surrounding Sicily are normally perturbed by cyclones that originate from interactions between air masses with different temperatures which contrast with the high temperature of sea water.

CALMET simulations are performed by using observed meteorological data of temperature, relative humidity, wind direction and speed from 80 wind stations covering the whole Sicily region.

The profilometric data are provided by an upper-air station of the Servizio Meteorologico dell'Aeronautica Militare sited near the Trapani Birgi airport. This allows to get a good characterization of the vertical intensity profile and wind direction. Moreover, measurements from 12 stations of WMO (World Meteorological Organization), at 10-m height above ground level, and 4 stations of Mareografic at 10-m height above ground near the coast are used. For a total coverage of the Sicily region, CALMET makes use of data from on-surface stations of the SIAS grid (Servizio Informativo Agrometeorologico Siciliano). In particular, we have considered all those stations that provide measurements of wind speed at 10 m above the ground (an overall total of 29 station distributed on regional scale), and 34 stations that perform measurements of wind speed at 2 m for those areas with low coverage by SIAS monitoring stations with measures at 10 m. Fig. 4 shows above described measuring points.

In a domain with a 3x3 km resolution cell, three-dimensional meteorological fields are evaluated with hourly time step for one year. MPI index layers are simulated for ten years, from 2010 to 2019, to obtain a more consistent set of results.

Attention is paid to choose of the parameter called TERRAD, which is specified by the user. TERRAD is related to the highest gridded terrain height within a radius of influence used by the CALMET model to compute the following parameters as suggested in (Martorana et al., 2020): kinematic effects of terrain, slope flow effects and blocking effects on the wind field.

Analyses performed using QGIS software about ridge-to-ridge distances across hills of neighbouring cells allowed an evaluation of TERRAD value of 2.5 km.

Moreover, some parameters of CALMET model are set according to the guidelines included in the U.S. EPA (Irwin, 1998; Bridgers, 2016).

To determine the accuracy of the simulated wind speed, we have evaluated the index of agreement (AI) (Willmott et al., 1985) that measures how well the variability in the model simulations matches that in the observed data, can vary between 0 and 1, with 1 representing a perfect agreement of wind speeds at all grid points. In mesoscale model applications, a value of AI greater than 0.5 is considered to be typical for a successful simulation of wind speed (Lyons et al., 1995; Shafran et al., 2000; Wang et al., 2008).

AI results in our work have range from 0.6 and 0.7, demonstrating the good performance of the simulations.

3.1 Overlap of MPI and thematic maps

Fig. 5 shows results of MPI index normalized by using ten quantile and, in particular, the different tones of green colour represents quantiles that go from 1 to 10. MPI index scores are approximately normally distributed.

Moreover, in Fig. 5, the maps of zones classified as special protection Natura 2000 and archeologic protection are shown.

Natura 2000 is a set of sites of community interest (SCI) created by European Union for the protection and conservation of habitat and animal and vegetable species, identified as priority from member states of European Union. Established under Regulation (EU) 92/43/CEE "Habitat", Natura 2000 allowed, in particular, to detect SCI which were successively named as Special Zones of Conservation (SZC). SZC include Special Protection Zone (SPZ) Established under Regulation (EU) 2009/147/CE "Birds" regarding conservation of wild birds.

The cartography of SPZ and SZC for the Sicilian territory is shown in Fig. 5 with areas coloured in yellow and archeologic protection zones are coloured in red.

Results reported in Fig. 5 show that western Sicily, excluding province of Palermo city, has large areas with high affinity. Such areas are mostly part of the province of Trapani city. Similar considerations can be extended to areas in province of Agrigento city and in province of Ragusa city.

As regards eastern Sicily, this has large zones characterised by stagnation phenomena (i.e. zones with low MPI index). Consequently, is possible deduce a low capacity of this territory at natural responding towards anthropic impacts.

Even if Trapani and Agrigento provinces have a good meteorological aptitude, overlapping MPI with maps relative to Natura2000 and archeologic protection zones, we deduce as follows:

- as regards inland zones in Trapani province, some ZSC areas are characterized by high MPI values;
- many zones in province of Agrigento are characterised by high MPI values but they overlap ZSC areas or archeologic protection.

Finally, seismic hazard map for Italian national territory is reported in Fig. 6 (Ordinanza PCM of the 28th of April 2006 n.3519, All.1b) together with last three quantile of MPI index reported, in grey. The colours from light blue to dark purple, indicates the different level of seismic hazardousness, as shown in legend.

This map, developed by Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (INGV) in collaboration with many Italian universities, officially became the reference map for the national territory with the emanation of law PCM 3519/2006 (G.U. n.105 on the 11th of May 2006).

Overlapping map allows to deduce that some geographic areas of Trapani (see Fig. 5 to locate Trapani city, north-east coast of Sicily) together with areas in the province of Agrigento (south coast of Sicily), are characterised by a medium seismic hazard and high MPI values.

Coast zones of provinces of Messina and Catania (see Fig. 5 to locate Messina and Catania, northwest coast of Sicily) and areas in province of Ragusa and Siracusa territories (see Fig. 5 southeast coasts), are characterised by

high and very high seismic hazard. Therefore, these areas are not a good choice for the realisation of industrial plants like those took into account in this paper.

4. Coherence of MPI with maps of Global Wind Atlas

The verification of MPI model capability to link areas with intense time-averaged wind flows on large scale areas is performed by a consistency analysis with wind maps carried out by web-based application Global Wind Atlas (<https://globalwindatlas.info/>).

Global Wind Atlas (GWA) is based on re-analysis data by using e ERA5 dataset from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) in the period 2008-2017. The data, located on a grid with a spacing of approximately 30 km, are used to force the WRF (Weather Research and Forecasting Model) mesoscale model using a grid spacing of 3 km. Next, the modelling process is made up of a WAsP (Wind Atlas Analysis and Application Program) calculation of local wind climates for every 250 m at five heights: 10 m; 50 m; 100 m; 150 m and 200 m (Lange and Højstrup, 2001).

WAsP was developed by Danish Meteorological Organization's Risø to estimate wind characteristics and power productions from wind turbines (Mortensen et al., 1993).

Figs 7 and 8 report, for the Sicily region, GWA maps of mean wind speed at 10 and 50 m above ground level, respectively.

GWA map at 10 m, reported in Fig. 7, highlights that the majority of Sicilian territories is characterised by low values of wind speed (from 1.0 to 2.5 m/s). The areas where average wind speed exceeds 8 m/s (zones coloured in yellow, red and white of Fig. 7) fall into geographical areas characterized by mountain ranges or with high orographic complexity. However, these areas have a limited extension and all of them are contiguous with areas characterized by very low average wind speeds.

This condition is maintained at 50 m (see Fig. 8) in some areas of the provinces of Messina, Catania and Caltanissetta cities. However, it is noted that the provinces of Trapani, Agrigento, Ragusa and Siracusa cities are marked by large areas where average wind speed exceeds 6 m/s (zones coloured in white).

Above results are congruent with data of MPI map. In fact, geographical territories around of Trapani, Agrigento, Ragusa and Siracusa cities are characterized by highest values for quantile distributions of MPI index (see Fig. 5).

In fact, are highlighted those geographical areas that have common characteristics i.e. large territories with similar characteristics in terms for which high wind speeds and so zones high rates of air interchange against zones with low interchange.

It is worth highlighting that all areas with high average wind speed (greater than 8 m/s) and with limited extension of Fig. 8 (area of few kilometers and often with a quasi-linear distribution) are characterized by low values of MPI index of fig. 5 (areas coloured in white and light green with quantile from 1 to 4). This outcome is justified by the capability of the model to taken into account if a cell $c[i,j]$ of the grid receives meteorological pressures from nearby cells as well as to give more importance to those wind directions that affect this cell with more frequency.

In fact, if a single point of this territory is analysed by using wind rose diagrams generated by GWA and compared with wind rose diagrams of the bordering points, it is possible to notice that among them there's strong lack of uniformity in terms of wind speed, direction and frequency. But of course, this type of comparison becomes increasingly difficult to do and interpret if several points on large areas are taken into consideration.

Because study disaggregated data it is not always practical or feasible, MPI seem to be a suitable alternative.

5. Conclusions

A new meteorological pressure index (MPI), derived by a combination of the wind speed, direction and frequency in a 3D domain, has been developed to identify neighbouring areas that are characterized by environmental similarities in terms of 3D wind fields (specifically zones high rates of air interchange against zones absence of any interchange) and so with resilience capacity in terms of pollutant transport phenomena connected to natural wind actions.

In environmental impact assessments or environmental feasibility analysis, it is often made resorted, for example, to wind rose to better understand meteorological observations as wind speeds and directions. However, wind roses diagram offers a form of meteorological fingerprint that changes from place to place. If wind roses come from neighboring areas against the reference point it is customary to take an average of the wind roses from surrounding observations. In this case, wind rose will give information as for the relative distribution of wind directions and not the real level of the mean wind speed. However, these data become difficult to interpret in cases of complicating terrain where mountains and valleys running in completely different directions. Moreover, by using rose wind diagram, there's no way for achieving information about areas with high rates of air interchange against zones absence of any interchange.

As a reply to this need, MPI is a tool useful to identify neighbouring areas on large scale that are characterized by environmental similarities in terms of 3D wind fields and, in addition, comes in handy to define maps that, for example, can link impacts, or cases of lack of impacts, with maps related to emission sources in regional air pollution modelling.

MPI application in Sicily region, Italy, as a case study, has allowed to identify areas highly predisposed to stand up in a natural manner against the pollution and consequently areas that are eligible to house an incinerator plant. By the way, it is worth noting that MPI is calculated by using 3D wind field evaluated by CALMET model that takes into account parameters as kinematic effects of terrain, slope flow effects and blocking effects on the wind field.

To make the verification of MPI model capability to link areas with intense time-averaged wind flows, consistency of MPI results are tested by analyses of maps performed by Global Wind Atlas are carried out.

These analyses have allowed to confirm good MPI capability to aggregate meteorological data on a regional level.

It is worth highlighting that these results allow to open the way towards the use of the tool proposed in this paper for environmental feasibility analyses concerning other facilities in the process industry that produce atmospheric pollution, offering a point of view useful to support the decision making.

Tables

Table 1 Linguistic terms and input fuzzy sets related to Wind Speed, WS [m/s] (Giardina et al., 2019).

<i>Linguistic value of WS [m/s]</i>	<i>Fuzzy linguistic number</i> $(x_1; x_2; x_3); (x_1; x_2; x_3; x_4)$	<i>Weight</i> p_{WS}
Very Low (VL)	(0; 1.5; 3.3)	0.2
Low (L)	(1.5; 3.3; 6)	0.4
Medium (M)	(3.3; 5.5; 7; 10)	0.6
High (H)	(6; 9.5; 11; 14)	0.8
Very High (VH)	(10; 14; 100; 100)	1

*Triangular and trapezoidal fuzzy numbers are indicated with (x_1, x_2, x_3) e (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4) , respectively

Table 2 Linguistic terms and input fuzzy sets related to Wind Frequency, WF [%] (Giardina et al., 2019).

<i>Linguistic value of WF [%]</i>	<i>Fuzzy linguistic number</i> $(x_1; x_2; x_3); (x_1; x_2; x_3; x_4)$	<i>Weight</i> p_{WF}
Very Low (VL)	(0; 0; 5; 10)	0.2
Low (L)	(5; 10; 15)	0.4
Medium (M)	(10; 15; 20)	0.6
High (H)	(15; 20; 25)	0.8
Very High (VH)	(20; 25; 100; 100)	1

Table 3 Linguistic terms and output fuzzy sets related to MPI index (Giardina et al., 2019).

<i>Linguistic value of MPI [-]</i>	<i>Fuzzy linguistic number</i> $(x_1; x_2; x_3); (x_1; x_2; x_3; x_4)$	<i>Weight</i> p_{MPI}
Very Low (VL)	(0; 0.1; 0.2)	0.111
Between Very low and Low (VL_L)	(0.1; 0.2; 0.3)	0.222
Low (L)	(0.2; 0.3; 0.4)	0.333
Between Low and Medium (L_M)	(0.3; 0.4; 0.5)	0.444
Medium (M)	(0.4; 0.475; 0.525; 0.6)	0.556
Between Medium and High (M_H)	(0.5; 0.6; 0.7)	0.667
High (H)	(0.6; 0.7; 0.8)	0.778
Between High and Very High (H_VH)	(0.7; 0.8; 0.9)	0.889
Very High (VH)	(0.8; 0.9; 1; 1)	1

FIGURES

Fig. 1. Structure of a typical fuzzy system.

Fig. 2. Schematization of cell $c[i,j]$ in the calculation domain used for computing of $MPI[i,j]$ (Giardina et al., 2019).

Fig. 3. Process flow chart for MPI index computing.

Fig. 4. Networks stations used for simulations performed by using CALMET model.

Fig. 5. Overlapping map of MPI index in green, ZSC areas cartography in yellow and archeologic protection zones in red.

Fig. 6. Overlapping map of MPI index, in green, with cartography of seismic vulnerability areas.

Fig. 7. Global Wind Atlas map of mean wind speed at 10 m above ground level for Sicily region.

Fig. 8. Global Wind Atlas map of mean wind speed at 50 m above ground level for Sicily region.

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